

EXPERIMENTAL MECHANICS IN ENGINEERING AND BIOMECHANICS

**Proceedings ICEM20
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Porto 2-7 July 2023**

Editor

J.F. Silva Gomes

**INEGI-FEUP
(2023)**

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INDICATORY SURFACE OF ANELASTIC-ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF SiO₂, NANOCOMPOSITES OF MULTIWALLED CARBON NANOTUBES AND POLYAMIDE, POLYETHYLENE, POLYVINYLCHLORIDE, POROSITY POLYSTYRENE

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ABSTRACT

The results of examinations of the relaxation processes in a crystalline lattice at thermal and ultrasonic processing on the temperature spectrum of internal friction Q^{-1} and elastic modulus E of SiO₂ nanocomposites, temperature dependencies of internal friction $Q^{-1}(T)$ and elastic modulus $E(T)$ (indicatory surfaces of anelastic-elastic properties are presented).

Keywords: anelastic-elastic properties, internal friction, nanocomposite, carbon nanotubes.

INTRODUCTION

The non-destructive internal friction (IF) Q^{-1} method is related to the reservoir prospecting and exploration technologies and reservoir productivity parameters analysis of the positions of IF maximums Q^{-1}_M , the relaxation time τ and their contribution to the damping of elastic vibrations [1-3]. The influencing of ultrasonic (US) deformation ϵ_{US} was researched on anelastic and elastic characteristics of nanocomposites of multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT).

RESULTS

The temperature dependencies of IF $Q^{-1}(T)$ (Figure 1) and elastic modulus $E(T)$ (Figure 2) (indicatory surfaces of anelastic-elastic properties) SiO₂ are presented in Figures 3 and 4.

Fig. 1 – Temperature dependence of internal friction $Q^{-1}(T)$ in SiO₂.

Fig. 2 – Temperature dependence of elastic modulus $E(T)$ SiO₂.

Fig. 3 – Temperature dependencies of $Q^{-1}(T)$ and $E(T)$ (indicatory surface of anelastic-elastic properties) SiO_2 .

Fig. 4 – Temperature-pressure dependencies of elastic modulus $E_{001} = \rho(V_{P[001]})^2$ (indicatory surface of elastic properties) SiO_2 .

CONCLUSIONS

As the result of the mechanical study, the presence of a strong effect between polyamide-6 ($NH(CH_2)_5CO$)_n, polyethylene (C_2H_4)_n polyvinylchloride (C_2H_3Cl)_n and multiwalled carbon nanotubes was confirmed.

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